

TEVSAPHIL IN THE PHILIPPINES

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Abstract: *Skills are vital for poverty reduction, economic recovery and sustainable development. As a consequence, policy attention to technical and vocational education and training (TVET) is increasing worldwide. Vocational education is education that prepares people to work in a trade, a craft, as a technician, or in professional vocations such as engineering, accountancy, nursing, medicine, architecture, or law. Craft vocations are usually based on manual or practical activities and are traditionally non-academic but related to a specific trade or occupation. Vocational education is sometimes referred to as career education or technical education. Vocational education can take place at the secondary, post-secondary, further education, and higher education level; and can interact with the apprenticeship system. Until recently, almost all vocational education took place in the classroom, or on the job site, with students learning trade skills and trade theory from accredited professors or established professionals. However, online vocational education has grown in popularity, and made it easier than ever for students to learn various trade skills and soft skills from established professionals in the industry.*

INTRODUCTION

The education system in the Philippines embraces formal and non-formal education. It is closely related to the American mode of education but differs in the number of school years as other countries have 12 years basic education. In the country however, elementary education is composed of 6 years and secondary education is 4 years which together with the tertiary education comprise the formal education system. On the other hand, non-formal education includes education opportunities, even outside school premises, that facilitate achievement of specific learning objectives for particular clienteles, especially the out-of-school youths or adult illiterates who cannot avail of formal education. An example is functional literacy programmes for non-literate and semi-literate adults which integrate basic literacy with livelihood skills training

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education, and higher education level; and can interact with the apprenticeship system. Until recently, almost all vocational education took place in the classroom, or on the job site, with students learning trade skills and trade theory from accredited professors or established professionals. However, online vocational education has grown in popularity, and made it easier than ever for students to learn various trade skills and soft skills from established professionals in the industry.

Wilhelm von Humboldt's educational model goes beyond vocational training. In a letter to the Prussian king, he wrote: "There are undeniably certain kinds of knowledge that must be of a general nature and, more importantly, a certain cultivation of the mind and character that nobody can afford to be without. People obviously cannot be good craftworkers, merchants, soldiers or businessmen unless, regardless of their occupation, they are good, upstanding and – according to their condition – well-informed human beings and citizens. If this basis is laid through schooling, vocational skills are easily acquired later on, and a person is always free to move from one occupation to another, as so often happens in life. The philosopher Julian Nida-Rümelin criticized discrepancies between Humboldt's ideals and the contemporary European education policy, which narrowly understands education as a preparation for the labor market, and argued that we need to decide between "McKinsey", to describe vocational training, and Humboldt.

TEVSAPHIL

- TEVSAPHIL :Technical Vocational School Associations of the Philippines
 - There are 4,406 Technical Vocational (TVET) Schools in the Philippines
 - 4,005 TVET Schools, 90.9 % are private.
 - About 60% of the TVET schools are members of TEVSAPHIL
 - Alejandro "Alex" T. Escaño is the President/Chairman of TEVSAPHIL
- Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Situationer

Region	Number of Registered Programs			Number of TVET Institutions		
	WTR	NTR	Total	Private	Public	Total
NCR	3,404	1,176	4,580	1,099	36	1,135
CAR	325	165	490	133	15	148
I	1,408	57	1,465	237	27	264
II	509	7	516	85	22	107
III	1,598	487	2,085	407	29	436
IV-A	2,069	217	2,286	491	30	521
IV-B	512	10	522	79	19	98
V	1,300	108	1,408	208	35	243
VI	853	78	931	177	37	214

Region	Number of Registered Programs			Number of TVET Institutions		
	WTR	NTR	Total	Private	Public	Total
VII	772	292	1,064	219	39	258
VIII	674	30	704	94	39	133
IX	784	34	818	124	23	147
X	764	17	781	145	22	167
XI	764	39	803	193	21	214
XII	922	26	948	180	5	185
CARAGA	437	31	468	61	29	90
ARMM	160	6	166	38	8	46
TOTAL	17,255	2,780	20,035	3,970	436	4,406

I. Distribution of Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) by Region

2. Distribution of Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) by Ownership

3. Distribution of Private Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) by Region

4. Distribution of Public Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) by Region

5. Distribution of Registered Programs by Region

6. Distribution of Registered Programs by Sector

7. Distribution of TVET Programs by Type of Registration

8. Distribution of Registered Programs by Region - With Training Regulation (WTR)

9. Distribution of Registered Programs by Region - No Training Regulation (NTR)

Sectors with Biggest Number of Registered Programs

Tourism	– 5,087 (29.5%)
Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	– 4,186 (24.3%)
Health, Social and Other Community Devt. Services	– 3,363 (19.5%)
Construction	– 1,170 (6.8%)
Metals and Engineering	– 878 (5.1%)
Automotive	– 827 (4.8%)
Electronics	– 575 (3.3%)
Agriculture and Fishery	– 249 (1.4%)
Others (Decorative Crafts, Footwear and Leathersgoods, Furniture and Fixtures, Garments, HVAC, Land Transport, Maritime, Processed Food and Beverages, Pyrotechnics, Utilities, Wholesale and Trading)	– 920 (5.3%)

11. Certified TVET Trainers (Level I) by Region

Region				
	Private	Public	Total	% Share
NCR	3,710	325	4,035	14.69%
CAR	457	397	854	3.11%
I	1,459	785	2,244	8.17%
II	924	771	1,695	6.17%
III	773	567	1,340	4.88%
IV-A	1,812	563	2,375	8.65%
IV-B	469	376	845	3.08%
V	1,042	532	1,574	5.73%
VI	1,055	767	1,822	6.63%

12. Certified TVET Trainers (Level I) by Region

Region				
	Private	Public	Total	% Share
VII	1,774	558	2,332	8.49%
VIII	583	714	1,297	4.72%
IX	708	512	1,220	4.44%
X	957	424	1,381	5.03%
XI	1,476	549	2,025	7.37%
XII	868	293	1,161	4.23%
CARAGA	609	447	1,056	3.84%
ARMM	143	63	206	0.75%
TOTAL	18,819	8,643	27,462	100%

13. Certified TVET Trainers (Level I) by Sector

	TOTAL	% Share
Agri-Fishery	869	3.16%
Automotive & Land Transport	1,763	6.42%
Construction	2,585	9.41%
Electronics	1,019	3.71%
Footwear &Leathergoods	1	.003%
Garments	453	1.65%
Health, Social and other Community Development Services	6,798	24.75%
HVAC	283	1.03%
ICT	3,741	13.62%
Maritime	125	0.46%
Metals & Engineering	2,013	7.33%
ProcessedFood and Beverages	472	1.72%
Tourism	7,340	26.73%
TOTAL	27,462	100%

14. TVET Enrollment and Graduates by Region:

Region	2010			
	Enrollment	% Share	Graduates	% Share
NCR	305,336	19.46%	232,661	17.31%
CAR	40,954	2.61%	40,780	3.03%
I	67,479	4.30%	62,559	4.65%
II	74,667	4.76%	69,882	5.20%
III	123,168	7.85%	131,287	9.76%
IV-A	251,000	16.00%	222,242	16.53%
IV-B	61,330	3.91%	52,736	3.92%
V	56,418	3.60%	41,669	3.10%
VI	67,788	4.32%	50,977	3.79%

15. TVET Enrollment and Graduates by Region:

Region	2010			
	Enrollment	% Share	Graduates	% Share
VII	176,603	11.26%	142,498	10.60%
VIII	54,086	3.45%	50,835	3.78%
IX	82,742	5.27%	72,330	5.38%
X	66,091	4.21%	57,990	4.31%
XI	34,964	2.23%	22,330	1.66%
XII	64,460	4.11%	54,689	4.07%
CARAGA	41,531	2.65%	38,906	2.89%
ARMM	-no data-	-	-no data-	-
TOTAL	1,568,617	100%	1,344,371	100%

16. Persons Assessed and Certified by Priority Sector:

Priority Sector	2010		
	A	C	Certification Rate
Agriculture & Fishery	13,688	9,629	70.3
Automotive	65,575	49,915	76.1
Construction	36,469	30,230	82.9
Electronics	23,455	15,679	66.8
Footwear and Leathergoods	-	-	-
Furniture	14	14	100
Garments	6,921	5,567	80.4
Health	164,240	149,074	90.8
HVAC-R	7,228	6,267	86.7

Persons Assessed and Certified by Priority Sector: 2010

Priority Sector	2010		
	A	C	Certification Rate
ICT	60,884	32,501	53.4
Maritime	77,124	75,015	97.3
Metals and Engineering	41,321	33,441	80.9
Tourism	210,201	178,570	85
Processed Foods	9,100	8,421	92.5
Utilities	-	-	-
Others	-	-	-
Total	716,220	594,323	83.0

CONCLUSION

Finally, besides the internal needs of TESDA, training consumers, training institutes, stakeholders and policy makers also needs regular information to enable them to make informed decisions. Information such as the following should be regularly provided and disseminated: (a) what training are available; (b) how much does it cost to acquire training on specific fields; and (c) how training providers perform in terms of competency assessment and employment at the program level. Improve capacity for monitoring and evaluation As TESDA focuses more on regulation and strategic financing, there will be a continuous need to design and test regulatory and financing instruments. There is therefore a need to systematically build capacity in TESDA to continuously design better instruments, test them and analyze their impacts rigorously. This would include capacities for both ex-ante regulatory impact analysis and ex post impact evaluation analysis. Improve the Image of TVET To this day the image of TVET is low compared to college and university education. There is a need to formulate a strategic communication plan to uplift the image of TVET. Clarifying better its role in development.

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